

Electronic lab books from a user's perspective

Results of a needs analysis at the Berlin University Alliance

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Introduction

The Berlin University Alliance¹, a consortium of universities and a hospital in Berlin, has set itself the task of providing researchers at the alliance's universities– Freie Universität Berlin (FU)², Humboldt University of Berlin (HU)³ and Technical University of Berlin (TU)⁴ as well as Charité University Medicine Berlin (Charité)⁵ with the infrastructure required for research data management and to ensure its long-term availability.

For some time now, and with increasing relevance, this infrastructure has included electronic laboratory notebooks (ELNs) – the digital continuation of the paper laboratory notebooks that have been widely used to date, particularly in the disciplines of chemistry, physics and microbiology. Laboratory notebooks serve to fully document the experiments carried out in the course of projects, including their results. In this way, they support accurate and careful working practices, making them an essential component of good scientific practice (German Research Foundation, 2025). At the same time, research data is made available for reuse, in line with the FAIR principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016).

ELNs extend the functionality of paper laboratory notebooks through features enabled by their digital nature, such as comprehensive searchability, electronic signatures, and integration with external systems for data transfer and analysis. Due to their flexibility in use and the adaptability of their user interfaces, ELNs are becoming increasingly attractive to disciplines that have previously documented research data using other methods, for example through written protocols. As a result, ELNs can function as central data hubs within research infrastructures, contributing to improved data quality and more efficient reuse of research data.

However, ELNs are not yet widely used within the BUA. One exception is Charité, which has access to a centrally administered instance of the ELN LabFolder⁶ via the Berlin Institute of Health⁷. This ELN is also used at the FU, but in two departments only. Beyond that, there are a few instances of various ELN systems used in research groups.

The lack of widespread use of ELNs and the implementation of different systems influence the conditions for consistent documentation, standardisation and reuse of research data, while also hindering collaboration within the BUA. To counteract this, the introduction of a state-of-the-art system for documenting research data is urgently needed. For this purpose, suitable

¹ Website of the Berlin University Alliance. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/>.

² Website of Freie Universität Berlin. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.fu-berlin.de/>.

³ Website of Humboldt University of Berlin. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.hu-berlin.de/>.

⁴ Website of the Technical University of Berlin. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.tu.berlin/>.

⁵ Website of Charité Universitätsmedizin Berlin. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.charite.de/>.

⁶ Website of ELN LabFolder. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.labfolder.com/de>.

⁷ Website of the Berlin Institute of Health (BiH). Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.bihealth.org/>.

ELNs are being piloted at Humboldt University in Berlin as part of the CARDS (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support) project⁸.

At the beginning of this project, alongside an evaluation of common ELNs (Paßmann & Alshawaf, 2025), a survey was conducted among researchers at the BUA to find out what they expect from an ELN. This included aspects such as user-friendliness as well as a wide range of functions that enable or simplify the workflow and documentation of research data. This publication summarises the results of this survey and discusses them in the context of the FAIR principles, among other things.

Methods

Survey

For the survey, we used the ELNFinder⁹ developed at TU Darmstadt as a basis to draft 40 questions in German and English addressing the needs of researchers. The questions were grouped into seven categories (e.g., user-friendliness, general management, data security, research data management, integration and extension using tools). Participants could respond using free-text fields as well as single- or multiple-choice options.

"General management" referred to aspects of ELNs that relate to collaboration, standardised procedures, working processes and corresponding tools or connections to devices. "Research data management", on the other hand, covered aspects such as the use of controlled vocabulary and ontologies as well as metadata, but also counterfeit protection. A complete list of all questions and answer options is available for download on Zenodo as part of the publication.

After the questions had been drafted, they were submitted for review and comment to the staff councils and data protection officers of all institutes participating in the survey (Technical University of Berlin, Humboldt University of Berlin, and Free University of Berlin; see next section).

The survey was conducted using the LimeSurvey (LimeSurvey GmbH, n.d.) instance of Humboldt University of Berlin and took place between 28 March and 1 May 2025. The links (German and English versions) to the survey were sent by email (if known or available) to the secretariats of the research groups involved in the pilot project, with the request that they be distributed to all members of the research group. In order to obtain a picture of the needs as realistic as possible, Master's and Bachelor's students were explicitly excluded from the survey. The reason for this is their lack of experience in implementing research projects and

⁸ Website of the BUA-funded project CARDS (Collaboratively Advancing Research Data Support). Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.berlin-university-alliance.de/commitments/sharing-resources/shared-resources-center/CARDS-FDM/index.html>.

⁹ ELN Finder at TU Darmstadt. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://eln-finder.ulb.tu-darmstadt.de/home>.

the resulting expectation that these status groups would not be able to comment on the necessary documentation options.

All responses were stored anonymously. In addition, IP addresses were anonymised to prevent participants from taking part in the survey more than once.

Participants

The survey was conducted among researchers who participated in the piloting of electronic lab books as part of the CARDS project of the Berlin University Alliance. A total of 39 research groups were contacted randomly, of which nine agreed to participate in the pilot project. The participants came from the Technical University of Berlin, Humboldt University of Berlin and the Free University of Berlin. Researchers from Charité University Medicine Berlin did not participate in the survey, as no research group agreed to participate in the pilot project.

The survey was started a total of 38 times, but only completed 32 times. The incomplete surveys were not included in the evaluation. The participants were recruited from different status groups, with PhD students and postdoctoral researchers forming the largest group (see **Table 1**).

Table 1. Demographic overview of participants in the needs survey on electronic lab books.

Status group	N	Number of research groups from...	N
Professor	3	Technical University of Berlin	4
Research group leader	1	Humboldt University of Berlin	3
Postdoctoral researcher	9	Free University of Berlin	2
Research assistant	1		
PhD students	16		
Laboratory technician	1		
Data manager	1		
Subject areas		Languages	
Biology	17	German	16
Chemistry	9	English	16
Biology-related (life sciences, biotechnology)	3		
Other	1		

The research groups involved in the pilot project represented only a few disciplines (biology, chemistry and related sciences), where at least one participant was from the field of materials science. The survey was completed in both German and English ($N = 16$ each).

Due to data protection regulations and the requirements of the staff councils of all participating institutes, no personal data was requested. Therefore, information on gender and age distribution is missing. Participants were asked, though, how many years of experience they had with management systems and electronic laboratory notebooks (see **Table 2**).

Table 2. Number of years of experience with management systems and in the use of electronic lab books.

Years	Management	ELNs
No experience	4	1
< 1 year	3	1
1-2 years	4	3
2-4 years	7	6
4-8 years	3	13
8-12 years	4	4
> 12 years	2	4

Note: Since the question about experience with management systems was not mandatory, there is a difference of $N = 5$ compared to the number of fully completed questionnaires.

Analysis

The responses were analysed using R (version 4.4.2; R Core Team, 2021) together with the packages dplyr (version 1.1.4; Wickham et al., 2025a) and tidyr (version 1.3.1; Wickham et al., 2025b). The results reflect the number of responses submitted per response category. For multiple-choice questions, this means that the total number of responses may exceed the number of participants in the survey. For multiple-choice questions, participants were also given the option of writing answers in free text fields that were not covered by the options provided. The results are presented across all status groups. For the supplements, an additional evaluation was carried out with regard to the individual status groups in order to reflect differences in the response behaviour of the groups.

Results

The results of the needs survey across all status groups are presented below, grouped according to question categories.

General

As noted above, years of experience in management differ from experience with ELNs (see **Table 2**). When comparing both aspects, a clear clustering along similar ranges of experience is particularly evident in the categories 2–4 and 4–8 years (see **Figure 1A**), driven mainly by the PhD student group (see **Figure 1B**).

Figure 1. Strength of correlation between years of experience with management systems (x-axis) and electronic lab notebooks (y-axis). A) across all status groups, B) broken down by status group. ReAs, research assistant. $N = 32$.

The data further show that PhD students tend to have more experience with ELNs than with management systems in general, whereas the opposite pattern is observed among postdoctoral researchers. Furthermore, the results show that the laboratories participating in the pilot study primarily collect and analyse experimental research data ($N = 31$), followed by microscopy data ($N = 22$), genetic data ($N = 17$) and chromatographic data ($N = 16$). Simulation data ($N = 6$) and image data ($N = 5$) were also mentioned. In addition, structural and spectroscopic data, method sequences, laboratory protocols, models and specific formats such as NMR, IR, UV-Vis, MS, HPLC, GC and GC-MS were mentioned in the free text fields.

MS Office formats are the most commonly used data formats ($N = 30$), closely followed by plain text formats ($N = 27$; see **Figure 2A**). CSV ($N = 17$) and TSV ($N = 15$) formats are also widely used. In addition, formats such as JSON ($N = 8$), XML ($N = 6$), RData ($N = 5$), and ODT ($N = 3$) were mentioned. Highly discipline-specific formats, including GBK, FASTA, FASTQ, CDXML raw, as well as various image, video, and audio formats, were also reported.

Figure 2. Overview of the storage formats and storage locations used by the research groups for their research data. A) Storage formats, B) Storage locations for research data of the research groups. $N = 32$.

The majority of the data is stored locally in the research groups ($N = 28$), although USB ($N = 23$), institute-owned storage ($N = 22$) and cloud services ($N = 20$) are also in use (see **Figure 2B**). In contrast, the research groups' own NAS servers ($N = 9$), repositories (institute-owned: $N = 5$; external: $N = 1$) or external cloud services ($N = 3$) are used less frequently.

When asked about responsibility for research data-related tasks within their groups, most participants identified PhD students ($N = 31$) and postdoctoral researchers ($N = 28$) as primarily responsible for data collection, followed by laboratory technicians ($N = 24$) and student assistants ($N = 23$). Data managers, on the other hand, rarely bear responsibility for this task ($N = 4$). Similar patterns were observed for data entry, data cleaning, quality control, and the processing and analysis of research data (see **Figure 3**).

These results show that central tasks along the data life cycle are mainly performed by PhD students and postdoctoral researchers. The results also indicate that the research data infrastructure used is still structurally more geared towards individual practice than standardised processes, and underline the need for support systems for documentation, quality assurance and reuse of research data.

Figure 3. Distribution of tasks in the research groups with regard to the collection and processing of research data. $N = 32$.

User-friendliness

Software adoption is strongly influenced by user-friendliness, which primarily relates to adaptability to users' specific needs (Nielsen, 1994). This aspect was also considered important by the majority of participants ($N = 21$). In this context, templates in the ELN are a particularly helpful feature, as recurring information and experimental procedures can be stored and retrieved from the ELN as needed, which simplifies data input. This is also very popular among the participants (see **Figure 4A**), all of whom consider the creation of their own templates to be important ($N = 32$). The ability to import existing templates, either from one's own research group ($N = 25$) or from the internet ($N = 14$), is also considered relevant. For many, subject-specificity is of particular importance ($N = 23$), which is also reflected in the mention of microtiter templates ($N = 17$).

Another key factor influencing acceptance is the ease and intuitiveness of data entry within an ELN (see **Figure 5A**). Most participants preferred text-based input ($N = 31$), tables ($N = 29$), or drawings and sketches ($N = 25$). Given the strong representation of chemistry-focused researchers, input via a chemistry-specific editor was also frequently mentioned ($N = 16$). Nevertheless, other forms of data entry were also considered suitable. These included scientific calculators ($N = 17$) and the use of internal (e.g., on local data carriers; $N = 16$) and external links to research data (e.g., to repositories or cloud services; $N = 15$). Bar scanners ($N = 9$) and calendars ($N = 6$) were considered less relevant. In addition, codes ($N = 2$), image files, free text entries and formalised and automatically readable measurement value fields ($N = 1$ each) have been mentioned as well.

Figure 4. Participants' preferences regarding the aspects A) use of templates, B) offline entry and storage of research data, C) operating systems for an ELN, and D) languages offered in the ELN. $N = 32$.

If data is already available in digital form, the most popular import methods are drag & drop ($N = 31$) or searching via the file browser ($N = 30$), although importing from emails is also widely accepted ($N = 10$, see **Figure 5B**). In this regard, importing from websites (e.g., with regard to products; $N = 1$) or the automated entry of devices using REST API (or ftp and similar protocols if the data originates from a non-local device, for example; $N = 1$ each) is of little interest to participants.

When entering data manually, participants would like ELNs to support text ($N = 31$), table ($N = 28$) and image formats ($N = 32$) in particular, as well as structured formats (such as c/tsv formats; $N = 26$, see **Figure 5C**). That classic MS Office formats were mentioned very frequently ($N = 23$) is probably due to their widespread use. Support for video formats ($N = 20$), compressed formats (e.g., zip, tar.gz, etc.; $N = 19$) and scientific formats (e.g., scientific notation e^{-10} ; $N = 17$) was also requested, whereas audio formats were rather not ($N = 8$). A few wanted the option of storing code formats (e.g., as Jupyter Notebook; $N = 1$) or image files (e.g., png, jpg, tif; $N = 1$). And it was noted that data formats should not be restricted at all, as various formats are useful for samples and experiments.

Although offline data input is highly desirable ($N = 19$), more participants would prefer the option of offline storage ($N = 23$; see **Figure 4B**). Almost all participants expect English to be available as a language ($N = 31$; German: $N = 22$, see **Figure 4D**), whereby it seems to be irrelevant whether an ELN can run on Windows ($N = 26$) or MacOSX ($N = 25$). Linux, on the other hand, as an operating system is less demanded ($N = 13$, see **Figure 4C**).

For data export, most participants prefer formats for long-term archiving (e.g., txt, c/tsv; $N = 30$, see **Figure 5D**) – slightly fewer expect corresponding formats for publications (e.g., docx, odt or pdf; $N = 28$). Less than half of the participants ($N = 11$) wanted machine-readable formats (e.g., json), which is probably due to the low awareness of these formats. In this regard, the generation of links for data sharing was also mentioned.

In summary, users primarily understand user-friendliness in functional terms: they want flexible, easily accessible input and import options as well as adaptability to existing workflows. ELNs are thus primarily perceived as tools to support established practices, not as instruments to enforce new workflows.

Figure 5. Participants' preferences regarding aspects A) data input, B) import methods for research data, C) input formats for research data, and D) formats for exporting research data. $N = 32$.

General management

Various aspects of effective management (e.g., laboratory equipment, collaboration between researchers, etc.) and their implementation in an ELN are an essential component for documentation and thus for the success of a project.

Rights management ($N = 23$) and role management ($N = 22$) were considered important by many participants (see **Figure 6A**), particularly to support collaboration between researchers. At least half of the participants ($N = 16$) also valued the use of comment functions and some also expressed a desire for ELNs to support the creation of multiple projects that can be collaboratively edited by different users.

The majority of participants ($N = 27$) welcomed the integration of standard operating procedures (SOPs) into an ELN, with a clear preference for project-specific versions ($N = 23$; see **Figure 6B**). Project-independent SOPs ($N = 16$) and graphical representations of SOPs ($N = 15$) were also supported by approximately half of the participants. In addition, participants noted that version control for SOPs would be useful, as procedures and workflows may change over the course of a project, making it easier to trace which SOP version was used for a given experiment.

When it comes to general management tools integrated into an ELN, calendars ($N = 20$) and task boards ($N = 19$) were mentioned most frequently, followed by project and task managers ($N = 17$ each, see **Figure 6C**). A tool for visualising milestones would also be a valued feature, at least for some ($N = 12$). In addition, there was a suggestion to add the option of connecting to project tools such as openProject¹⁰ or Kanban boards¹¹. Nevertheless, one participant in the survey found it sufficient to view ELNs purely as a documentation and data storage tool, without overloading them with management features.

Laboratory-specific functions were also in high demand, likely reflecting the strong representation of biology- and chemistry-focused research groups (see **Figure 6D**). The most frequently mentioned feature was the creation of a sample database ($N = 24$), followed by sample tracking ($N = 19$), equipment inventory lists ($N = 17$), equipment management (e.g., booking laboratory equipment; $N = 16$), and freezer management ($N = 15$). The option to place orders directly via an ELN was considered less relevant ($N = 8$).

In general, the integration of external devices into an ELN was viewed positively ($N = 24$), with Python-based solutions mentioned most frequently ($N = 17$; see **Figure 6E**). REST APIs ($N = 8$) and command-line interfaces ($N = 9$) were requested less often. Additional mentions included Java-based integrations ($N = 5$) and other APIs ($N = 3$). Last but not least, this category also addressed the issue of automation to simplify workflows (see **Figure 6F**). Automated data transfer was widely supported ($N = 21$). Device control and automated data analysis ($N = 9$

¹⁰ Website of OpenProject. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.openproject.org/de/>.

¹¹ Definition of Kanban board on Miro.com. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://miro.com/de/agile/was-ist-ein-kanban-board/>.

each) as well as automation on demand ($N = 10$) were appreciated by at least some participants.

Figure 6. Participants' preferences regarding the aspects A) collaboration, B) standard organising procedures (SOP), C) management functions, D) laboratory management functions, E) connection options and F) automation. $N = 32$.

In summary, management functions in ELN are particularly well received where they directly support collaboration and everyday laboratory work, for example through role and rights management, project-specific SOPs and basic planning and administration functions. At the same time, it appears that ELNs are not (yet) seen as fully-fledged project management tools, but primarily as support systems for research-related processes.

Integration of/extension using tools

The interfaces described above primarily support the integration of external tools. Approximately half of the participants indicated that integration with Git¹² ($N = 17$) or Jupyter¹³ ($N = 15$) would be desirable to support data analysis and documentation of analysis scripts. The integration of development environments similar to Visual Studio Code was also suggested. In addition, a majority of participants supported the integration of graphics software ($N = 21$) and links to scientific journals and reference management tools ($N = 24$).

Participants whose research focus was in chemistry ($N = 17$) were additionally asked about chemistry-specific tools to be integrated into ELNs (see **Figure 7A**). Among the suggested options, ChemDraw tool¹⁴ was preferred most frequently ($N = 13$), followed by PubChem¹⁵ and CAS SciFinder¹⁶ ($N = 7$ each). Other tools mentioned included ChemDoodle¹⁷ ($N = 4$), Chemaxon's Marvin JS¹⁸ and/or MarvinSketch¹⁹ ($N = 2$ each), as well as Ketcher²⁰, RDKit²¹, Reaxys²² and Open Babel²³ ($N = 1$ each).

Participants were also asked whether additional subject-specific tools would be desirable. Gene-specific tools such as SnapGene²⁴ ($N = 17$) and general analysis tools for DNA and genes ($N = 14$) being named most frequently – Jalview²⁵ ($N = 1$; see **Figure 7B**) was mentioned as

¹² Git website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://git-scm.com/>.

¹³ Jupyter website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://jupyter.org/>.

¹⁴ ChemDraw website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://revvitysignals.com/products/research/chemdraw>.

¹⁵ PubChem website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://pubchem.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>.

¹⁶ CAS SciFinder website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.cas.org/solutions/cas-scifinder-discovery-platform/cas-scifinder>.

¹⁷ ChemDoodle website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.chemdoodle.com/>.

¹⁸ Chemaxon's Marvin JS website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. https://chemaxon.com/marvinsketch_js.

¹⁹ Chemaxon's MarvinSketch website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. https://chemaxon.com/marvinsketch_js.

²⁰ Ketcher website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026.

<https://lifescience.opensource.epam.com/ketcher/index.html>.

²¹ RDKit website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.rdkit.org/>.

²² Reaxys website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.elsevier.com/de-de/products/reaxys>.

²³ Open Babel website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://openbabel.org/index.html>.

²⁴ SnapGene website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.snapgene.com/>.

²⁵ Jalview website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.jalview.org/>.

well. In contrast, support for the the Atlas Chromatography Data System²⁶ ($N = 4$) and PlasMapper²⁷ and NWA Quality Analyst²⁸ ($N = 1$ each) was limited.

In addition, eight participants indicated that the option to integrate custom plugins into an ELN would be beneficial, while it was also noted that the integration of AI-based tools, such as ChatGPT²⁹, could be advantageous as well.

Figure 7. Participants' preferences for the integration of A) tools for chemistry and B) other subject-specific tools into an ELN. N/A, not applicable. $N = 32$.

Data security

Data security is a major concern for survey participants. Above all, they expect password-protected access to the ELN ($N = 30$; see **Figure 8A**). In contrast, stronger protection mechanisms such as multi-factor authentication were considered less relevant ($N = 6$), although one participant noted that this could be useful for projects with particularly high security requirements. The option of single sign-on via federated authentication services such as Shibboleth³⁰ was also viewed positively, as was the possibility of granting separate access to researchers from outside one's own institution.

When it comes to the storage location of research data, most participants wanted an ELN to primarily enable connections to the institution's own storage services ($N = 26$) or cloud services ($N = 25$; see **Figure 8B**). The option of local storage space ($N = 17$) or institute-owned

²⁶ Atlas Chromatography Data System website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026.

<http://apps.thermoscientific.com/media/SID/Informatics/PDF/DS-ATL610.pdf>.

²⁷ PlasMapper website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://plasmapper.wishartlab.com/>.

²⁸ NWA Quality Analyst website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://www.nwasoft.com/products/nwa-quality-analyst>.

²⁹ ChatGPT website. Last accessed on 09.01.2026. <https://chatgpt.com/>.

³⁰ Definition of Shibboleth on Wikipedia. Last accessed on 09.01.2026.

<https://de.wikipedia.org/wiki/Shibboleth>.

repositories ($N = 13$) is also accepted. However, the option of USB ($N = 7$) or NAS ($N = 6$) as storage locations seemed to be less relevant.

Most participants preferred to access the ELN either via a web browser of their choice or through a locally installed application ($N = 27$ each; see **Figure 8C**). It was noted that a standalone application would be unnecessary if the browser-based version functions reliably. Another participant highlighted the usefulness of supporting private browser windows, which would allow multiple users to enter data on a shared computer. In addition, a majority of participants supported the availability of a mobile application, for example for use on tablets ($N = 19$).

Figure 8. Participants' preferences regarding the security of their research data. A) login, B) storage location of research data, C) access to the ELN. $N = 32$.

Research data management

With regard to aspects of research data management, the main focus was on preferred implementations in the areas of forgery protection, metadata, ontologies and controlled vocabulary.

With regard to forgery protection, participants primarily expressed a preference for time stamps ($N = 16$), version control ($N = 13$), and electronic signatures ($N = 11$; see **Figure 9A**). In contrast, log recording ($N = 6$) and data access accreditation ($N = 5$) were considered less important. Regarding the standardised documentation of research data using metadata, subject-specific vocabulary or ontologies, the answers were strongly influenced by participants' experiences in this area. There was only moderate support for the integration of ontologies ($N = 11$) and subject-specific vocabulary ($N = 15$) into ELNs.

Figure 9. Participants' preferences regarding aspects of research data management. A) forgery protection, B) metadata for publication, C) metadata for data collection, D) metadata for standards and identification. $N = 32$.

Support for metadata, though, varied depending on the type of metadata considered. Metadata related to publication received particularly high approval (see **Figure 9B**), with

publication title and year ($N = 22$ each), as well as author name and journal title ($N = 21$ each), mentioned most frequently. Somewhat fewer participants considered the institution name ($N = 17$), publication issue ($N = 16$), and department name ($N = 14$) to be relevant. Two participants noted in this context that ELNs may be less suited as tools for publishing data.

Metadata related to data collection were similarly valued (see **Figure 9C**). Both the date of data collection ($N = 24$) and the time and name of the researcher collecting the data ($N = 23$ each) were considered particularly relevant. This was followed by data type ($N = 17$), data format ($N = 15$), and data size ($N = 14$). Notably, subject-specific metadata were considered relevant by nearly half of the participants ($N = 15$), whereas the location of data collection played only a minor role ($N = 6$).

Metadata related to identity and standards were considered less relevant overall (see **Figure 9D**). These included project descriptions ($N = 14$), persistent identifiers (PIDs) for researchers (e.g., ORCID³¹) or publications (e.g., DOI³², $N = 12$ each) and project numbers ($N = 10$). Additional mentions included PIDs for research institutions ($N = 7$), funding organisation names ($N = 6$), language, file version, and third-party rights ($N = 5$ each), as well as publication licences and PIDs for repositories and funding organisations ($N = 4$ each). Geological coordinates were mentioned by only one participant.

Again, the results show a clear focus on aspects of immediate practical relevance, such as timestamps, version control and publication-related metadata. In contrast, more standardising elements such as ontologies, controlled vocabulary or comprehensive metadata schemas are only selectively considered relevant.

Discussion

The results of the needs survey allow the expectations placed on electronic laboratory notebooks to be contextualised against the backdrop of concrete research practices within the participating research groups at BUA institutions. Across all subject areas, a consistent pattern emerges: requirements for ELNs are primarily shaped by immediate, task-related work processes rather than by abstract or overarching concepts of research data management. ELNs appear to be understood primarily as a supporting infrastructure that reflects and stabilises existing practices, rather than as tools for fundamentally redesigning workflows.

The different roles of the status groups, whose tasks within a research group are closely related to the various aspects of the research data life cycle³³, appear to be a key factor in shaping these expectations. PhD students and postdoctoral researchers are significantly involved in all aspects of this cycle, e.g., the operational collection, processing and analysis of

³¹ ORCID – Persistent Identifier for Researchers. Last accessed on 09.01.2026 . <https://orcid.org/>.

³² DOI – Persistent identifier for publications. Last accessed on 09.01.2026 . <https://www.doi.org/>.

³³ Research data lifecycle. Last accessed on 09.01.2026 . <https://forschungsdaten.info/themen/informieren-und-planen/datenlebenszyklus/>

research data. Accordingly, they value flexible, versatile functions that can be adapted to changing experimental requirements. Professors and research group leaders, on the other hand, view ELNs more from a higher-level perspective, in which robustness, traceability and coverage of fundamental processes are the main focus. Other status groups, such as laboratory technicians or data managers, show less differentiation in their requirements overall, which is probably related to their more specific responsibilities within the research group and thus also within the data life cycle. These status group-dependent perspectives seem to explain most of the preference patterns observed.

With regard to user-friendliness, it becomes clear that participants primarily understand this concept in functional terms. What matters most is not a wide range of complex features, but rather the ability to work with familiar data formats, simple import mechanisms, and customisable structures. This orientation reflects the desire to efficiently transfer existing documentation routines into an ELN, rather than to establish new, system-driven working methods. Accordingly, high acceptance is expected particularly where ELNs are perceived as a low-threshold extension of existing practices.

A similar picture emerges in the area of general management. Participants expressed a preference for lean, research-oriented functions that support collaboration within projects and the organisation of everyday laboratory work, for example through role and rights management or project-specific SOPs. In contrast, comprehensive project management or control functions are not necessarily viewed as a core responsibility of an ELN. From the users' perspective, ELNs are therefore not intended to function as universal management systems, but rather to remain clearly focused on documentation and research-related processes.

Requirements in the area of research data management complement this practice-oriented overall picture. Particularly relevant are functions that support traceability and transparency in data collection and processing, such as time stamps, version control, and selected metadata with direct relevance to publication and data acquisition. In contrast, more strongly standardising elements, such as ontologies or controlled vocabularies, are only considered relevant by a subset of participants. This suggests not a fundamental rejection of such concepts, but rather their limited integration into current research routines.

Overall, there is a clear correlation between the needs expressed and the principles of comprehensible and reusable documentation of research data. At the same time, it becomes visible that more extensive requirements for standardisation and interoperability have played only a minor role in practice so far.

The significance of the results is severely limited by the small sample size and the subject-specific orientation of the research groups involved in this survey. The findings cannot therefore be easily transferred to all disciplines or institutions of the Berlin University Alliance. Nevertheless, they offer insight into the expectations of key user groups and provide an empirical basis for the further selection, configuration and introduction of electronic lab books in an institutional context.

Summary

The results of the needs survey conducted during the BUA-funded pilot phase of the CARDS project indicate a clear preference for established, widely used, and flexibly adaptable tools that can be seamlessly integrated into existing workflows. Given the disciplinary focus of the participating research groups on biology and chemistry, discipline-specific features such as chemical editors, gene-related analysis tools, and laboratory and sample management functions are considered particularly relevant components of an electronic laboratory notebook.

Across all subject areas, user-friendliness is understood primarily in terms of functionality. The focus is on flexible input and import options, support for common data formats, and individual customisation through templates to reflect existing documentation practices. In this context, ELNs are primarily perceived as tools to support established working methods rather than instruments for introducing new workflows.

In the area of general management, there is a focus on lean, research-related functions that facilitate collaboration and organisation in everyday laboratory work, for example through role and rights management and project-specific SOPs. Comprehensive project management functionalities, on the other hand, are not formulated as a central expectation of an ELN.

Requirements in the area of research data management focus in particular on aspects of traceability, transparency and publication-related documentation, such as time stamps, version control and selected metadata. More extensive standardisation approaches, such as the use of ontologies or controlled vocabulary, are only selectively considered relevant.

Overall, the results show that participants primarily view electronic laboratory notebooks as a supporting infrastructure within existing research practices. Their added value lies in their ability to stabilise documentation, quality assurance, and the reuse of research data across individual working methods and personnel changes, thereby supporting key requirements of the FAIR principles.

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Appendix

The following section lists the aspects discussed in the publication from the needs analysis, broken down by status groups.

Appendix 1. Participants' preferences regarding aspects A) use of templates, B) offline entry and storage of research data, C) operating systems, and D) languages offered in the ELN, broken down by status groups. ReAs, research assistant; spec., specific. $N = 32$.

Appendix 2. Participants' preferences regarding aspects A) data input, B) import methods for research data, C) input formats for research data, and D) formats for exporting research data, broken down by status groups. ChemEdit, chemical editor; compr., compressed; DrawSketch, drawing/sketch editor; ReAs, research assistant; scient., scientific; struct., structured. $N = 32$.

Appendix 3. Participants' preferences regarding aspects A) collaboration, B) standard organising procedures (SOP), C) management functions, D) laboratory management functions, E) connection options and F) automation, broken down by status groups. If no information was provided, the status group did not answer the corresponding questions. DB, database; Funct., function; man., manager; ReAs, research assistant; track., tracking. $N = 32$.

Appendix 4. Participants' preferences for the integration of A) tools for chemistry and B) other subject-specific tools into an ELN, broken down by status group. If no information was provided, the corresponding questions were not answered by the status group. N/a, not applicable; ReAs, research assistant; SciFi, Scifinder. $N = 32$.

Appendix 5. Participants' preferences regarding the security of their research data, broken down by status group. A) login, B) storage location of research data, C) access to the ELN. MFA, multi-factorial authentication; ReAs, research assistant; repo, repository; uni, university. N = 32.

Appendix 6. Participants' preferences regarding aspects of research data management, broken down by status group. A) forgery protection, B) metadata for publication, C) metadata for data collection, D) metadata for standards and identification. Where no information was provided, the status group did not answer the corresponding questions. Depart., department; geol. coord., geological coordinates; inst., institute; PID, persistent identifier; proj., project; publ./public., publication; repo, repository. $N = 32$.